

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Genetic nature of some agronomic traits in two elite lines of rice

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We studied the genetic nature of some agronomic traits using elite lines A 69-1 (P1) and IR31868-64-2-3-3-3 (P2) to efficiently exploit the variation in breeding materials. P1 combines well for salt tolerance. P2 is a high-yielding variety with good grain quality and resistance to major pests and diseases.

Thirty plants from the F₂ between the lines were randomly chosen. Each was backcrossed to its parents and to the F₁. The families of the P1, P2, F₁, F₂, BC₁ (F₁/P1), and BC₂ (F₁/P2) were studied. We transplanted and raised 10 plants from seeds of nonsegregating materials and 30 from seeds of segregating ones. The field experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design and replicated three times. Plants were spaced at 20 × 20 cm and fertilized at 80-40-0 kg NPK/ha.

Means of the studied traits were lower for F₂ than for F₁ and the better parent (Table 1). Backcrosses to the better parent produced higher values for all traits than backcrosses to the poorer parent. Results indicate scope for selecting parents and the possibility of getting heterotic lines.

Estimates of gene effects indicate highly significant dominance effects (Table 1). Additive × additive was significant among the epistasis effects.

Because dominance × dominance is large and negative and dominance large and positive, the estimates of additive, additive × additive, and additive × dominance should be mentioned without duplicate type of nonallelic interaction.

High variation occurs because of dominance and epistatic effects for all these traits. Selection in later generations

Table 1. Means of the basic generations and estimates of the genetic components.^a

Generation	Yield (g/plant)	Panicles (no./hill)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Panicle length (cm)	Plant height (cm)	Growth duration (d)
P1	19.6	9	95	30.2	27.4	114.0	135
P2	20.2	14	78	21.7	23.8	94.2	124
F ₁	33.5	14	119	27.3	26.2	114.9	133
F ₂	21.3	13	87	25.9	25.8	100.8	130
BC ₁	28.1	14	107	27.3	26.4	112.4	133
BC ₂	26.3	16	92	24.9	25.5	100.3	128
Estimate							
Mean	21.3**	13.1**	87.4**	25.9**	25.8**	100.8**	129.5**
Additive	1.8	-2.5	14.6	2.4*	0.9	12.1	4.5
Dominance	37.2**	10.1**	81.5**	2.2*	1.4**	33.0**	8.2*
Additive × additive	23.6**	7.6**	48.4**	0.8	0.5	22.2**	4.2*
Additive × dominance	2.0	0.0	5.9	-1.9	4.9	2.2	-1.0
Dominance × dominance	-25.6**	-16.5**	-35.3**	1.3	-0.7	-9.6*	-2.4

^a* and ** = significant at 5 and 1% levels.

Table 2. Equality test between the means of triple testcross families and basic generations.^a

Test	Yield	Panicles/hill	Filled grains/panicle	1000-grain wt	Panicle length	Plant ht	Growth duration
$\bar{L}_1 - \bar{BC}_1$	2.47*	0.85ns	-0.80ns	-0.20ns	0.38ns	-2.30ns	-0.90ns
$\bar{L}_2 - \bar{BC}_2$	-0.66ns	-1.10ns	-0.90ns	0.00ns	0.10ns	0.40ns	-0.20ns
$\bar{L}_3 - \bar{F}_3$	4.35**	2.04**	3.90ns	-1.00**	-0.20ns	-0.10ns	-1.40ns

^a* and ** = significance at 5 and 1% levels, ns = nonsignificant.

would be better to diminish dominance effects.

We tested for linkage by comparing the grand means of triple testcross families \bar{L}_1 (F₂/P1), \bar{L}_2 (F₂/P2), and \bar{L}_3 (F₂/F₁) and those of the basic generations

\bar{BC}_1 , \bar{BC}_2 , and \bar{F}_2 . Linked epistatic genes were present for all characters except grain yield (Table 2). The significant differences in grain yield expressed a linked digenic interaction. ■

Stability analysis for irrigated rice yield

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We evaluated the stability of the performance of 14 medium-grain advanced lines and varieties from 1989 to 1991. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted on 10 Jul 1989, 12 Jul 1990, and 10 Jul 1991. Plots were 2 × 6.25 m², with 30 cm between plants and rows. Recommended agronomic and plant protection measures

Mean grain yield (t/ha) and estimates of stability parameters for 14 rice genotypes over 3 yr.^a

Genotype	\bar{X}	bi	Sd ²	r ²
PK3699-43	3.33	1.1452	0.0718	0.0577
PK3717-9	4.33	0.9737	0.0659	0.0721
PK3717-12	4.19	1.9294	0.7997	0.0235
PK3727-2	3.92	1.4145**	0.0409**	0.0224
PK3727-5	3.73	2.0643**	0.1195**	0.0304
PK3732-8	3.41	0.9639	0.0242	0.0285
PK3733-7	3.19	0.7764	0.0287	0.0508
PK3737-10	3.39	0.6054	0.0223	0.0641
PK3737-11	3.51	1.1380	0.0406	0.0339
PK3801-18	3.53	1.1779	0.0450	0.0351
PK3917-33	3.60	1.1082	0.0686	0.0588
PK3849-18	3.66	0.9441	0.0648	0.0752
IR6	3.19	-0.0787	0.0537	0.9059
KS282	4.13	-0.1677	0.5099	0.9529
Av	3.65	1.0000		0.1722

^a** = significantly different from 0 at 0.01 level of probability.